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RASPBERRY PI BASED FACE IDENTIFICATION ATTENDANCE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT - currently, industries, organisations are using personal identification strategies such as RFID, Iris recognition, Fingerprint identification is used for taking attendance. Among of all these personal identification strategies including face recognition is most natural, less time is taken and highly efficient one despite being difficult to implement, a continuous observation for overcoming it. It has several applications in attendance management system and security systems. In this work, a system is implemented that takes attendance for students during lecture, employees in industries and etc. using face detection and recognition technology. A time period is set for taking attendance and the data base is automatically uploaded into the web server through the internet connectivity. This process is done without any human intervention. In the system a Raspberry Pi installed with Open CV library and a Raspberry Pi Camera module is connected for facial detection and Recognition. The data is stored in the memory card connected to Raspberry Pi and it can be accessed through the internet. The results show that a continuous observation increases accuracy and maximizes the output.

Keywords – [RFID, Face Recognition, Detection, Accuracy, Open CV.]

1. Introduction

The current systems that are used for updating attendance automatically are usually RFID based, Bio-metric based and MATLAB based. Usually, the manual method of taking attendance is difficult and a time consuming process. Hence it is important to construct an efficient method for managing attendance automatically. Another advantage of the system is that inclusion of fake attendance can be prevented. Open Command Visualization (Open-CV) is an open source library in which the source code is open and it is useful in visual fields such as image processing. The main motto of this work is to take and manage attendance using face recognition

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Many organisations, companies and institutions are taking

periodic attendance using [1] RFID methods, [2] Biometric Fingerprint method and Registers. These methods generally take more time for calculation. RFID (Radiofrequency Identification) [1] uses electromagnetic fields to automatically identify and track tags attached to persons. RFID can violate the privacy and security of human beings. RFID strategies ultimately effect software that allow each person to be analysed by the primary data base. This environment can be easily affected by hackers. If RFID reader and receiver are not properly matched then less read rate occurs. Biometric fingerprint identification, [2] system employs fingerprint as a unique identity. It is one of the most accurate systems running effectively today. But recognition of an individual fingerprint from a set of enrolled fingerprints is a difficult process. The fingerprint system does not reveal any information regarding the original fingerprint. This may have been proved to be false as many algorithms [3] reveal that a fingerprint can be reconstructed with minute templates. Iris Recognition [4] is another type of implementation where the iris of people is scanned, stored and then retrieved for the comparison and attendance is managed automatically in the server. But there is difficulty in capturing iris of the student so employees and hence a fast implementation of face recognition [4] with decreased illumination effect can be used.

3. PROPOSED MODEL

The proposed system is used for taking attendance by using face recognition and managing the attendance in suitable environments such as colleges and offices. The system architecture is shown in Figure. Raspberry Pi Camera Module V2 attached to Raspberry Pi 3 and it is placed where the people enter the office.

Figure.1: Block diagram

Figure.2: Raspberry-pikit

Figure.3: LCD Display

Figure.4: Raspberry-piCameraModule

Camera Module is used to capture video from which images of human faces is extracted? Then face recognition takes place and it automatically verifies with the existing database through library files present in OpenCV. Face Recognition is generally more advanced and efficient than other systems. The steps involved are given as follows.

A. Capturing the image

The camera module is placed in a region where the people enter into college or office and video is taken within the distance less than 5 meters. A camera is used for taking video which contains many frames from which any one of the frames can be used for face recognition and marking the attendance.

B. Creating database

As a biometric method has been chosen for implementation, it is crucial for enrolment of every individual whose attendance needs to be taken. Here face of every individual is captured and stored in a suitable database which includes the person's name and other credentials. Here multiple samples are taken for a single individual with different lighting conditions. A database of 5 students along with 10 images of each individual persons.

C. Detecting Faces

Choosing an efficient algorithm for face recognition is critical in this proposed work. There are many face detection algorithms available in Open CV such as Eigen faces, Fisher faces and Local Binary Pattern Histograms. Considering the need for the real time recognition an algorithm which has been opted is the Haar Cascade Algorithm for face detection and recognition. It is available in Open CV source library and has proved to be robust.

Figure. 5. Project Image

Advantages

- Easiest method to keep track of attendance.
- Provides accurate attendance of the students.
- Proxy attendance is completely eradicated by this system.
- There are no physical interactions with the system.

Applications

- Smart industrial application.
- It is used in college level attendance.
- It is used in school attendance system.

Hardware

- Raspberry-Pikit
- Pi-Camera
- LCD Display
- IOT Module
- Transformer

Software

- Linux OS

Programming language: Python

CONCLUSION

Face recognition attendance systems can thus be proved to be secure and efficient. It gives a better recognition rate with a low false rate. Using Raspberry Pi independently improves the mobility of the work and it acts as stand alone hardware. The work can be further developed by improving recognition rate and by using Raspberry Pi Infra-Red camera module this system can be used as a security surveillance system.

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